

An assessment of pandemic risk perception among healthcare workers in teaching hospitals in Rivers State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Background: Healthcare staff face numerous challenges, placing them at risk of contracting the infection. The study investigated how health staff at Rivers State teaching hospitals regarded the pandemic's health threats.

Materials and Methods: This study involved healthcare workers (HCW) from teaching hospitals in Rivers State, Nigeria. To attract healthcare personnel, a multi-stage sampling technique was implemented. A descriptive cross-sectional study design was used to investigate health workers' views of pandemic risk. We employed a pretested standardized questionnaire. Cronbach's alpha coefficient was used to assess the reliability of the questionnaire for this study, and the result was 0.72, which is significant. The data gathered from participants was entered and analyzed with the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software version 25. The University of Port Harcourt's Research and Ethics Committee granted ethical approval for the experiment.

Results: The majority of interviewees (86.6%) acknowledged the risk of pandemics. There was a significant association between age ($p=0.0001$), marital status ($p=0.014$), sex ($p=0.0001$), tribe ($p=0.001$), religion ($p=0.033$), income ($p=0.0001$), professional category ($p=0.0001$), employment duration ($p=0.023$), and risk perception.

Conclusion: Healthcare personnel that took part in the study rated the risk of pandemics as high. During pandemics, teaching hospital administrators must ensure that health staff have a sufficient and appropriate working environment.

Keywords: Risk perception, Pandemics, Healthcare workers, Teaching hospitals, Rivers State, Nigeria

Introduction

Over the previous four decades, the world has seen multiple outbreaks of novel diseases (1). The number of high-risk infectious diseases is increasing as some of them resurface or arise (2). This increase is attributed to the difficulty in avoiding the spread of novel illnesses generated by interactions between humans, animals, and the environment (1). It has been claimed that roughly 175 species are linked to disease development, with 75% of them zoonotic (3). The

majority of these zoonotic disease outbreaks have been linked to increased human–animal contact (1). Zoonoses account for roughly 44%, 30%, 11%, 9%, and 6% of viruses, prions, bacteria, protozoa, fungus, and helminths, respectively (1).

Some zoonotic diseases have caused outbreaks, such as *Escherichia coli* O157 in the 1980s; in Hong Kong in 1997, an avian strain of influenza infection was detected (4).

West Nile virus infection first appeared in 1999, chikungunya fever sprang out in Italy in 2007, and Q fever swept across the Netherlands (1). Furthermore, virulent strains of new coronaviruses caused severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS) and Middle East respiratory syndrome coronavirus (MERS-CoV) in 2002 and 2012, respectively (5). Avian influenza infections, including A/H1N1, occurred in Hong Kong in 1997, A/H7N7 in the United States in 2004, A/H7N2 in the United Kingdom in 2007, and A/H7N9 in China (5). Ebola virus disease (EVD) infection occurred in a few years, or half a decade, in African countries such as Nigeria and the Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC), resulting in thousands of cases and fatalities. The world is currently facing an unprecedented pandemic caused by a new strain of coronavirus known as Coronavirus Disease 2019 (7).

Risk Perception

Risk perception refers to people's ideas, attitudes, judgments, and emotions about dangers and diseases (8). Perception is a major factor in risk communication. Risk perception is a mental psychological construct that varies according to cognitive, emotional, socio-cultural, political, and personal factors (9). Individuals' emotions and instincts are said to influence their perception, which they gain through observation, situational analysis, and scientific consultation. Risk perception stems from ideas, attitudes, cultural sensitivities, and personal traits such as self-esteem and self-concept (10). Risk perception is a continuum from no risk to high danger, and it can influence decision-making both favorably and adversely. Healthcare workers (HCWs)' awareness and perception of the risk allow them to assess the current situation and make the best decision to reduce the risk to the lowest feasible level (11). However, in order to adopt healthy behavior, HCWs must be aware of the condition, recognize their vulnerability to it, and feel that it can be prevented or managed (12).

Furthermore, risk perception is a subjective judgment of the likelihood of a specific type of accident occurring and how concerned we are about the repercussions (13). Perceiving risk entails assessing both the chance and the repercussions of a bad result. It is also possible to claim that activity-related effects are part of risk perception. Perception of risk extends beyond the person and is a social and cultural construct that incorporates values, symbols, history, and ideology. Perceived risk is defined as the subjective determinant of predicted potential losses, with each scenario assigned a probability (15). Perceived risk has been highlighted in the HCW literature as a multidimensional process including multiple risk factors (16). When HCWs perceive a significant health

risk, they avoid particular health workers (17). Perceived risk has been calculated as the sum of perceived severity (magnitude), anxiety (feeling of worry or uneasiness), and efficacy (safety concerns) (16). During the SARS and HINI outbreaks, scholars utilized a variety of techniques to map risk perception. Anxiety is regarded a significant element in measuring perceived risk, whereas severity is a major predictor of risk perception (16).

The concept of risk perception can be explained using comparative optimism, often known as false optimism (18). It refers to the incorrect assumption that one's risk is lower than that of an average peer of the same gender and age (19). In general, optimistic biases contribute to risk underestimating, and people who perceive lesser risks are less likely to be interested in taking preventative measures (19). Personal control and comparative optimism play critical roles in risk perception and tolerance. As such, they are key concepts for comprehending health behavior (19). As a result, risk perception during a pandemic influences public psychology states. During an outbreak of an infectious disease, people frequently adjust their behavior to lower their risk of infection. Previous research demonstrated that risk perceptions of an infectious disease can predict a variety of preventative activities during an emergency pandemic (20).

The level of risk perception of infection has a significant impact on emotional concern, anxiety, and subsequent preventative measures. Recognizing the relevance of these disparities may help in creating effective treatments for motivating specific populations to practice preventive measures during epidemics (21). Although risk perception of infection can predict preventative measures, excessive risk perception can lead to anxiety and panic (22). Emotional worry may contribute to "emotional contagion" amongst communities during a period of collective concern. Understanding the specific characteristics that predict anxiety is critical for avoiding clinically significant anxiety. Furthermore, there is a high association between family and friend responses to the outbreak and personal preventive behaviors, emphasizing people' herd behavior. Risk perception is also critical for risk communication because it determines the risks people are concerned about and how they cope with them (22). Risk communication models such as risk perception, mental noise, negative dominance, and trust determination have been created to better understand how people perceive risk, process risk information, and make judgments about it (23).

Several factors can influence risk perception during a rising epidemic, including illness knowledge, information sources, and emotional components (24). Previous research has demonstrated a link between disease-specific information and perceived risk of

Middle East Respiratory Syndrome (25). Furthermore, dependable information sources serve as the foundation for acquiring credible knowledge and establishing social trust. False or misleading information may cause inflated anxieties or a lack of focus on a developing threat (25). Furthermore, psychological stress caused by a health emergency may influence risk judgment; additionally, accuracy of risk perception in the setting of imminent health concerns has been proposed, and people tend to overestimate the likelihood of unfavorable outcomes due to excessive emotional stress (26).

Pandemics

Pandemics are large-scale outbreaks of infectious illnesses that can cause significant morbidity and mortality across a vast geographic area (27). It produces widespread economic, social, and political disturbance (27). The majority of pandemics have been related to "zoonotic" disease transfer from animals to humans (28). Zoonoses can invade human populations through both domesticated animals and wildlife. Numerous historically significant zoonoses have been introduced as a result of increasing interaction between humans and animals caused by animal keeping at home, and high-risk zoonoses (such as avian influenzas) may continue to emerge as a result of animal rearing (29). Some viruses, such as Ebola, have developed from wildlife reservoirs and spread to humans through the hunting and ingestion of wild species (such as bushmeat), the wild animal trade, and other forms of contact with wildlife (30). Zoonotic diseases vary in their ability to survive and disseminate within human hosts.

Pandemics have happened throughout history and appear to be becoming more often, particularly due to the advent of viral illnesses in animals (31). Pandemic risk is determined by the interaction of spark risk (where a pandemic is likely to occur) and spread risk (how likely it is to spread widely throughout human populations) (31). Evidence suggests that the possibility of pandemics has grown over the last two decades due to increased global travel and integration, urbanization, changes in land use, and increased exploitation of the natural environment (32). These tendencies are likely to persist and deepen. The worldwide community has made progress in preparing for and minimizing the effects of pandemics (32). Despite efforts by numerous health parastatals, there remain significant gaps and obstacles in preparation for the worldwide pandemic (32). Multiple outbreaks, most notably the 2014 West African Ebola epidemic, have revealed gaps in disease detection, basic care availability, contact tracing, quarantine and isolation procedures, and preparedness beyond the health sector,

including global coordination and response mobilization (32). These gaps are particularly noticeable in resource-constrained contexts and have posed a risk in the event of a full-fledged global pandemic.

The inadequately prepared, uncondusive working environment, as well as other characteristics, have been associated to HCWs' elevated perceived risk of pandemic infections (33). Most HCWs get emotionally exhausted, which leads to medical errors, a lack of empathy when treating patients, and decreased productivity (34). This is reflected in a loss in the ability to provide critical healthcare services to patients (34). However, most hospitals in Nigeria, including those in Rivers State, do not provide appropriate protection for the well-being of HCWs, which is critical to guaranteeing the sustainability and quality of healthcare services. There is a substantial risk of infection since there is a significant gap in pandemic disease preventive and mitigation efforts (35). In addition, the countries' healthcare sectors are underfunded and poorly managed (36). There are few or no attempts to improve hygiene and preventive measures among HCWs, resulting in more disasters and even deaths from pandemics on a daily basis (37). However, a study of healthcare workers' risk perception of pandemics and the pertinent components can provide valuable insights to healthcare providers, health policymakers, and health and hygiene instructors (38). The study provided more information on how health personnel and the general public perceive the pandemic's risk.

Materials and methods

Study Area

This study was conducted among health personnel at the University of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital (UPTH) and Rivers State University Teaching Hospital (RSUTH) in Rivers State, Nigeria. Rivers State is one of Nigeria's 36 states, with its capital in Port Harcourt (39). The state's population was estimated to be 7,303,900 in 2016, ranking it sixth in the country (39). Rivers State is bordered by Imo, Abia, and Anambra states in the north, Akwa Ibom State in the east, Bayelsa and Delta states in the west, and the Atlantic Ocean to the south.

Rivers State has a diverse agroecological profile and is economically influential in the Niger Delta area (40). It is located at latitude 5°21'N and longitude 6°57'E and is one of the states in the South-South geopolitical zone and Niger Delta region. Rivers State is comprised of 23 Local Government Areas, including Port Harcourt LGA. Port Harcourt is Rivers State's largest city, with an urban population of around 1,865,000 people as of

2016. The city is located in the Niger Delta, along the Bonny River (39). Port Harcourt City is part of the Port Harcourt local government area, which consists of the former European quarters known as Old GRA and New Layout sections. Port Harcourt's urban area includes the Port Harcourt local government area as well as sections of Obio-Akpor and Eleme (39).

Port Harcourt is the medical services hub, and Rivers State has numerous hospitals and health institutions (39). Port Harcourt has two tertiary health facilities, sometimes known as teaching hospitals, as well as numerous more health facilities. The University of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital (UPTH) is located on East-West Road, Port Harcourt, Nigeria (41). It is a prominent tertiary-care teaching and research center in Rivers State. The University of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital began operations in 1980 and was officially commissioned by the federal government in 1985. When it began, there were 60 beds, the majority of which were in use (41). The University of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital is controlled under a three-tier system that includes the Board of Management, the Hospital Management Committee (HMC), and the Departments (39, 41). The hospital has the following departments: Accident and Emergency, Accounts, Administration, Anaesthesiology, Catering, Central Sterilization Service Department (CSSD), Communication, Community Medicine, Computer Science, Dentistry, Dialysis, Ear, Nose and Throat, General Out Patient Department, Intensive Care Unit, Internal Medicine, Laundry, Maintenance, Medical Illustration Unit, Medical Laboratory Services (Chemical Pathology, Haematology, and Blood Bank, Medical Microbiology and Parasitology, Anatomical Pathology), Medical Records, Medical Social Welfare, Neuropsychiatry, Nuclear Medicine, Nurse Practice Development Unit, Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Ophthalmology, Oral Maxillofacial, Orthopaedic Department, Paediatric Services, Pharmacy, Physiotherapy, Radiology, Stores, Surgical Department, Works and Services. The majority of clinics are staffed by consultants, senior registrars, junior registrars, matron nurses, other nurses, interns, and ward cleaners (39; 41). However, during the recent pandemic, the hospital set up a COVID-19 laboratory and isolation centre.

The Braithwaite Memorial specialized Hospital, renamed Rivers State University Teaching Hospital (RSUTH), is one of the hospital's oldest facilities, offering general, specialized medical and surgical treatments, as well as a variety of diagnostic and support services (42). The clinic has 731 medical staff members and 375 licensed beds. Its departments are Medicine, Laboratories, Paediatrics, Pathology, Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Radiology, Family Medicine, Surgery, Ophthalmology, Anaesthesia,

Accident Center, and Surgical/Medical Emergency (43). Other areas include pharmacy, maintenance, general administration, and finance. These Rivers State hospitals are located in Port Harcourt and provide health care, counseling, and referral services, as well as treatment and management of pandemic illnesses like COVID-19. (43).

Study design/Sampling method

The study followed a descriptive cross-sectional design. This study design was used to assess risk perception. This study used a multistage sampling procedure to select eligible individuals. Data was acquired using a standardized questionnaire. The sample size of 754 was obtained using Cochran's descriptive study sample size determination procedure.

Study tool and validation

The structured questionnaire was pre-tested with 75 participants, which represents 10% of the study's sample size. The reliability of the questionnaire in this study was evaluated using the index of internal consistency calculated with Cronbach's alpha coefficient, which yielded a significant result of 0.72.

Data analysis and interpretation

The data collected from the participants was entered into the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software version 25 and coded as numerical values. The data was analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25. Descriptive statistics were calculated and provided as frequencies and percentages. Inferential statistics, such as the chi-square test, were employed to investigate the relationship between socio-demographic factors and risk perception.

The following factors are often considered independent (age, gender, income, occupation, tribe, religion, marital status, education, professional category) because they can impact or explain differences in the dependent variable. However, the dependent factors influence the risk perception.

Ethical Considerations

The study received ethical approval from the University of Port Harcourt (UPTH) Research and Ethics Committee and the Rivers State University Teaching Hospital (RSUTH) Research Committee, and the eligible healthcare workers provided informed consent.

Results

Table 1 shows that the majority (41.6%) of the respondents were between the ages of 28 and 37; half (50.0%) of the study participants were married females, while more than half (54.2%) were males. While nearly half of the participants (45.8%) were Igbos, the vast majority (93.0%) were Christians.

Table 2 demonstrates that 76.4 percent of participants have a tertiary degree of education, whereas 29.2% earn \leq N50,000 and 50,001-N100,000, respectively. Among the professional group, many respondents (33.4%) are nurses, the majority of the study participants (74.9%) have worked $<$ 5 years, and the majority of the participants (41.8%) are at level 9.

Table 3 shows that the majority of respondents (98.0%) and (91.8%) admitted to avoiding crowded locations and close contact with anyone, as well as avoiding touching the eyes, nose, mouth, and contact with fluid, to prevent infection during the pandemic. Most (95.8%) participants maintain social/physical activities, whereas (95.9%) respondents cover their coughs/sneezes. More (98.7%) of the poll respondents agreed that isolating and treating people affected with pandemics are effective approaches to decrease the spread of illnesses. The table also shows that a large number (95.2%) of respondents admitted that staying informed and following advice given by your healthcare provider can reduce the chance of acquiring pandemic infections, a larger number (95.9%) of participants believe that practicing good hygiene is effective in protecting those around you from pandemic infections, and many (83.3%) of respondents believe that pandemics have serious negative consequences on their lives. Furthermore, the majority of study participants (83.4%) feel that pandemic infection is a serious sickness, and many (62.6%) expressed concern of catching diseases during the pandemic.

Table 4 indicates that many (37.4%) of the research respondents claimed that their job entails no direct contact with pandemic-infected patients in the hospital, and more (37.5%) are frightened that they will get the pandemic sickness. When compared to their colleagues of the same sex and age as themselves, more than half (58.2%) of respondents are less likely to contract pandemic disease, some (33.3%) of participants are undecided when compared to the local population of Africa, and a smaller number (24.9%) of respondents perceived that preventive measures against pandemic disease are effective.

Table 5 shows that several (37.4%) of the respondents are undecided on how serious the prognosis would be if they contracted the pandemic disease, while more than half (54.2%) of the participants think it is somewhat not difficult for pandemic infection to be transmitted from one person to another, some (33.2%) of the study

respondents stated they are personally unlikely to contract pandemic disease, and a much smaller number (16.8%) of the participants are somewhat confident.

Figure 1 reveals that the majority of participants (86.6%) perceived the risk of pandemics, while a small percentage (13.4%) did not.

Discussion

Main findings

This study discovered that practically all of the participants were aware of the possibility of pandemics and avoided crowded areas and close contact with others. Approximately (91.8%) of those who sensed the risk of the pandemic avoided touching their eyes, nose, and mouth, as contact with fluid inhibits infection during a pandemic. The majority of participants (95.8%) who sensed the risk of pandemics maintained social/physical contact, while 95.9% covered their lips while coughing or sneezing. The findings revealed that the majority of participants believe that isolating and treating people affected with pandemics are effective approaches to decrease the spread of illnesses. Almost all of the participants agreed that keeping informed and following their healthcare provider's recommendations can lower their chances of contracting pandemic diseases, and that practicing good hygiene can help protect those around them from pandemic infections. Furthermore, three-quarters of the individuals believed that the epidemic had a significant negative impact on their life. Furthermore, two-thirds of the healthcare workers who participated in this study believed that pandemic infection is a serious sickness, and 62.6 percent were afraid of catching infections during the pandemic.

Similar studies

The findings of this study are consistent with those of (38) who discovered that the majority of participants perceived the risk of becoming infected and the associated information. According to Puci (38), healthcare practitioners perceived the infection as high-risk. Furthermore, there is a similarity between the findings in this study and those of Simione and Gnagnarella (44) They reported that health personnel in Italy saw a high danger of COVID-19 dissemination. In addition, the HCW group assessed a higher danger (71%). Many HCWs (57%) were concerned about the health effects or mortality of being infected, but almost all (93%) were more concerned about their families, indicating a high perceived risk of infection. Similarly, a larger proportion of individuals (HCW), 73%, indicated a high perceived risk of infection. Furthermore, the findings by Abid and colleagues (45)

Table 1. Socio-Demographic Characteristics

Variable	Frequency (N=754)	Percentage (%)
Age (years)		
18-27	94	12.5
28-37	314	41.6
38-47	253	33.6
48-57	62	8.2
>57	31	4.1
Marital Status		
Single	253	33.6
Married	377	50.0
Separated	10	1.3
Widow	21	2.8
Widower	31	4.1
Cohabiting	62	8.2
Sex		
Male	409	54.2
Female	345	45.8
Tribe		
Igbo	345	45.8
Yoruba	30	4.0
Hausa	2	.3
Others	377	50.0
Religion		
Christianity	701	93.0
Islamic	31	4.1
Others	22	2.9

Figure 1. Overall risk perception of pandemics among healthcare workers

Table 2. Socio-demographic characteristics

Variable	Frequency (N=754)	Percentage (%)
Highest level of education		
None	5	0.7
Primary education	36	4.8
Secondary education	74	9.8
Tertiary education	576	76.4
Post Tertiary	63	8.4
Income (monthly)		
≤50,000	220	29.2
50,000	188	24.9
50,001-100,000	220	29.2
100,001-150,000	64	8.5
150,001-200,000	62	8.2
Professional Category		
Physician	95	12.6
Nurse	252	33.4
Med. Lab	32	4.2
Pharmacist	31	4.1
Community Health Worker	125	16.6
Management Staff	93	12.3
Support Staff	94	12.5
Security	32	4.2
Duration of Work in the Hospital		
<5years	565	74.9
6-14years	157	20.8
>25years	32	4.2
Level (at work)		
6	31	4.1
7	157	20.8
8	64	8.5
9	315	41.8
11	62	8.2
12	93	12.3
14	32	4.2

Table 3. Risk perception of pandemic among health workers

Variable	Yes Number (%)	No Number (%)
<i>Avoiding crowded places and close contact with anyone prevent the risk of infection during pandemics</i>	739(98.0%)	15(2.0%)
<i>Avoiding touching eyes, nose, mouth, and contact with fluid prevents infection during the pandemic</i>	692(91.8%)	62(8.2%)
<i>Maintaining social/physical distancing prevents the risk of infection with</i>	722(95.8%)	32(4.2%)
<i>Covering your cough/sneezing prevents the spread pandemics</i>	723(95.9%)	31(4.1%)
<i>Isolation and treatment of people who are infected with pandemics are effective ways to reduce the spread of the infections</i>	744(98.7%)	10(1.3%)
<i>Staying informed and following advice given by your healthcare provider can reduce the chance of acquiring pandemic infections</i>	718(95.2%)	36(4.8%)
<i>Following good hygiene is effective to protect the people around you from pandemic infections</i>	723(95.9%)	31(4.1%)
<i>I believe that pandemics have serious negative consequences on my life</i>	628(83.3%)	126(16.7%)
<i>I believe that pandemic infection is a severe disease</i>	629(83.4%)	125(16.6%)
<i>You perceived fear of contracting infections during the pandemic</i>	472(62.6%)	282(37.4%)

Table 4. Risk perception of pandemics among health workers

Variable	Frequency (n=754)	Percentage (%)
Work profile involves direct contact with pandemic-infected patients in the hospital		
<i>No Contact</i>	282	37.4
<i>Somewhat no Contact</i>	156	20.7
<i>Undecided</i>	63	8.4
<i>Somewhat Contacted</i>	190	25.2
<i>Contact</i>	63	8.4
Extent are you concerned that you might contract pandemic disease		
<i>No Concerned</i>	93	12.3
<i>Somewhat not Concerned</i>	94	12.5
<i>Undecided</i>	220	29.2
<i>Concerned</i>	283	37.5
<i>Much Concerned</i>	64	8.5
As compared to your colleagues of the same sex and same age as you, do you think you are more, less or as likely to contract pandemic disease		
<i>Much Less Likely</i>	126	16.7
<i>Less Likely</i>	439	58.2
<i>Undecided</i>	31	4.1
<i>Likely</i>	127	16.8
<i>Much Likely</i>	31	4.1
As compared to the local population of Africa, do you think you are more, less, or as likely to contract pandemic disease		
<i>No Concerned</i>	93	12.3
<i>Somewhat not Concerned</i>	157	20.8
<i>Undecided</i>	251	33.3
<i>Concerned</i>	221	29.3
<i>Much Concerned</i>	32	4.2
Perceived efficacy of preventive measures against pandemic disease		
<i>Not Effective</i>	158	21.0
<i>Somewhat not Effective</i>	125	16.6
<i>Undecided</i>	127	16.8
<i>Somewhat Effective</i>	156	20.7
<i>Effective</i>	188	24.9

Table 5. Risk perception of pandemics among health workers

Variable	Frequency (N=754)	Percentage (%)
Prognosis if you contracted pandemic disease		
<i>No Serious</i>	94	12.5
<i>Somewhat not Serious</i>	126	16.7
<i>Undecided</i>	282	37.4
<i>Somewhat Serious</i>	156	20.7
<i>Serious</i>	96	12.7
Pandemic infection can be transmitted from one person to another		
<i>Very Difficult</i>	95	12.6
<i>Somewhat not Difficult</i>	409	54.2
<i>Undecided</i>	188	24.9
<i>Somewhat Difficult</i>	31	4.1
<i>Difficult</i>	31	4.1
Personal likelihood of contracting pandemic disease		
<i>Very Unlikely</i>	96	12.7
<i>Unlikely</i>	250	33.2
<i>Undecided</i>	156	20.7
<i>Somewhat likely</i>	95	12.6
<i>Likely</i>	157	20.8
Exposed to pandemic disease, are you confident that you can, by personal skill or diligence, avoid infection		
<i>Not Confident</i>	63	8.4
<i>Somewhat not Confident</i>	125	16.6
<i>Undecided</i>	125	16.6
<i>Somewhat Confident</i>	127	16.8
<i>Confident</i>	314	41.6

Table 6. Association between Socio-demographic Characteristics and Risk Perception

Variables	Perception			X ²		Odd ratio (OR)
	Perceived risk (n(%))	No risk (n(%))	Total	df	(p-value)	95% (CI)
Age (years)						
≤47	596(90.2)	65(9.8)	661(100.0)	1	58.600 (0.0001) *	5.791 (3.549-9.449)
≥48	57(61.3)	36(38.7)	93(100.0)			
Total	653(86.6)	101(13.4)	754(100.0)			
Marital status						
Married	315(83.6)	62(16.4)	377(100.0)		6.048 (0.014) *	0.586 (0.382-0.900)
Unmarried	338(89.7)	39(10.3)	377(100.0)			
Total	653(86.6)	101(13.4)	754(100.0)			
Sex						
Male	313(76.5)	96(23.5)	409(100.0)	1	78.238 (0.0001) *	0.048 (0.019-0.119)
Female	340(98.6)	5(1.4)	345(100.0)			
Total	653(86.6)	101(13.4)	754(100.0)			
Tribe						
Igbo	283(82.0)	62(18.0)	345(100.0)	1	11.479 (0.001) *	0.481 (0.313-0.739)
Others	370(90.5)	39(9.5)	409(100.0)			
Total	653(86.6)	101(13.4)	754(100.0)			
Religion						
Christianity	602(85.9)	99(14.1)	701(100.0)	1	4.549 (0.033) *	0.238 (0.057-0.995)
Others	51(96.2)	2(3.8)	53(100.0)			
Total	653(86.6)	101(13.4)	754(100.0)			
Level of education completed						
Below Tertiary	102(88.7)	13(11.3)	115(100.0)	1	0.511 (0.475)	1.253 (0.674-2.328)
Above Tertiary	551(86.2)	88(13.8)	639(100.0)			
Total	653(86.6)	101(13.4)	754(100.0)			
Income						
≤150,000	561(89.3)	67(10.7)	628(100.0)	1	24.080 (0.0001) *	3.094 (1.938-4.941)
≥150,001	92(73.0)	34(27.0)	126(100.0)			
Total	653(86.6)	101(13.4)	754(100.0)			
Professional Category						
Clinical Staff	532(99.4)	3(0.6)	535(100.0)	1	261.544 (0.0001) *	143.625 (44.773-460.734)
Non-Clinical Staff	121(55.3)	98(44.7)	219(100.0)			
Total	653(86.6)	101(13.4)	754(100.0)			
Duration of Work						
≤14years	621(86.0)	101(14.0)	722(100.0)	1	5.169 (0.023) *	0.860 (0.835-0.886)
≥15years	32(100.0)	0(0.00)	32(100.0)			
Total	653(86.6)	101(13.4)	754(100.0)			
Level						
≤8years	213(84.5)	39(15.5)	252(100.0)	1	1.413 (0.235)	0.770 (0.499-1.186)
≥9years	440(87.6)	62(12.4)	502(100.0)			
Total	653(86.6)	101(13.4)	754(100.0)			

P≤0.05: statistically significant

are consistent with the current findings indicating there was perceived risk. They reported that around three-quarters of respondents (75% HCWs and 71% NHCWs, p-value 0.506) believe their families are at risk of infection. The results of this investigation are congruent with those of Abid and colleagues (45), who found that HCWs (83% frontline vs. 70% backend, p-value 0.003) assessed a risk of catching infection. The current conclusion is consistent with that of Asefa and colleagues (46) in Southwest Ethiopia, who showed that more than half (53.4%) of the participants had high-risk perceptions of infection. Similarly, Mindaye and colleagues (27) discovered that more than 58% of HCWs and support workers in the hospital perceived high-risk disease. According to Serwaa and colleagues (47) 68.3% of trial participants had a high risk perception of infection. Similarly, Usuwa and colleagues (48) reported a significant risk perception of infection. Another conclusion by Ezike and colleagues (2021), who discovered a significant perceived risk of infection, is consistent with the findings of this study. However, this agreement between current findings and earlier studies may be attributed to similarities in socio-demographic features, professional practice, healthcare trainings, availability of medical equipment and infrastructure, resources, etc.

Different studies

A study conducted by Imai and colleagues (49) demonstrated a low risk perception of infection. Our finding is not entirely consistent with the findings of our current investigation. The findings of Deressa and colleagues (50) in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia do not correspond to contemporary findings. They discovered that approximately 30% and 43% of the participants were somewhat or very concerned, respectively, that their health was jeopardized during the COVID-19 pandemic due to their work in the hospital. Lee and colleagues (51) showed that only 26.8% of participants evaluated the risk of pandemic infection, which is not comparable. Ali's (2021) study found that healthcare professionals who assessed low risk were better prepared for Ebola ($\chi^2=6.854$, $df=1$, $P=0.009$). According to Ali's (52) findings, the majority of healthcare workers who felt prepared had a lower perceived risk of infection (23%) than their unprepared colleagues, who had a higher perceived risk (35%). The disparity between the current and prior findings could be attributed to differences in socio-demographic factors, insufficient qualified healthcare workers, a lack of healthcare training, and an unequipped healthcare facility.

Strengths

The study focuses on a pertinent and important topic: healthcare personnel' risk perception during pandemics. It focuses on a vital population (healthcare professionals) who are at high risk during pandemics, making the study relevant to public health and healthcare system planning. A descriptive cross-sectional design was used, which is suited for determining the present status of risk perception at a given moment. Using a verified and pre-tested tool assures that the acquired data is reliable and valid. This indicates that the questionnaire has strong internal consistency, which ensures that the items consistently measure the concept of risk perception. The multi-stage sampling strategy includes healthcare workers from multiple professional categories and demographics, increasing the sample's representativeness. The study uses SPSS software (version 25) for statistical analysis, which is a powerful tool for examining quantitative data. The discovery of substantial connections between risk perception and different demographic and professional characteristics (e.g., age, gender, income, marital status, and professional category) enhances the study's findings. Ethical approval from the Research and Ethics Committee assures that the study follows ethical criteria, which increases credibility and acceptability. The high perceived risk (86.6%) emphasizes the urgent need for actions, making the data useful to policymakers. The considerable connections between demographics and risk perception give useful information for targeted treatments.

Limitations

The descriptive cross-sectional study design collects data at a single point in time, which limits the capacity to prove causation or track changes in risk perception over time. The study uses only quantitative methods (structured questionnaires and statistical analysis). It excludes qualitative data, such as interviews or focus groups, which could provide more detailed insights into the reasons behind risk perceptions. However, this study is important because it gives information for more robust and generalizable conclusions in future studies, particularly those using mixed-methods approaches and greater sample across varied healthcare settings.

Conclusion

According to the findings, the majority of healthcare personnel who participated in the study perceived a significant danger of pandemic infections. The anticipated increased risk of pandemic infections among healthcare professionals was linked to inadequate hospital working conditions and a lack of hospital consumables for effective healthcare service

delivery during the epidemic, such as sample bottles, gloves, and facemasks. Furthermore, the high risk of pandemic infections was associated with understaffing, work load and stress, a lack of trainings and coping techniques, a lack of current courses on pandemic preventive and control measures in hospitals, and the participants' socio-demographic characteristics.

Recommendations

During pandemics, health facility management should ensure that there are enough hospital consumables to provide adequate healthcare services. The amount of healthcare workers educated to address patient health situations during disease outbreaks or pandemics should be increased significantly.

Consent to publication

All of the authors are aware of the publishing.

Competing interests

There are no competing interests among the writers. The authors declared no conflicts of interest.

Ethical Code

The study followed the "do no harm" concept, ensuring that participants were not put at danger physically, psychologically, or socially as a result of their participation in the study. However, this study emphasized fairness and reduced bias in participant selection. Additionally, the ethical reference number is UPH/CEREMAD/REC/MM86/024.

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Authors' contribution

All authors contributed to the manuscript's design, analysis, interpretation, and preparation.

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